

earthaccess

Programmatic **search** and **access**
of NASA Earthdata in Python

Luis López et. al.
Research Software Engineer @ NSIDC

Software for the NASA Science Mission Directorate Workshop 2024

overview

NASA's Earth Observation data—collected continuously from satellites, aircraft, and ground-based missions for more than a half-century—constitute an invaluable record of Earth processes and a critical resource for scientists and researchers.

These data are currently being moved to AWS and are projected to grow the collection to approximately 250 PB by 2025 and to **more than 300 PB by 2030**,

But there is an issue...

Problem: data accessibility

Benjamin Cook

@DustyBowl

NASA Engineer #1: We're generating a lot of great data! How should we serve it?

NASA Engineer #2: How about we make sure users have to navigate two dozen dense and opaque webpages before they even get to a download link?

NASA Engineer #1: Brilliant!

10:34 AM · Mar 17, 2022

Dr. Benjamin works at NASA GISS and he's right!
<https://www.drbenjamincook.net/>

The power of **open science** only reaches its full potential if we have easy-to-use workflows that facilitate research in an inclusive, efficient and reproducible way.

Unfortunately —as it stands today— scientists and students alike face a steep learning curve adapting to systems that have grown too complex and end up spending more time on the technicalities of the tools, cloud and APIs than focusing on their important science.

Problem: API fragmentation (or lack of an API)

In order to programmatically access NASA datasets, new users must be familiar with:

- **Earthdata Login (EDL)**
 - How to use it with OAuth, CURL, WGET etc.
 - .netrc
- **Common Metadata Repository (CMR)**
 - How to query for what we want
 - How to read the metadata that CMR returns.
- **Cloud**
 - AWS
 - S3 buckets, S3 credentials
 - ...

Software
Engineer

Not a
Software
Engineer

Problem: cloud is complex

Credit: Patrick Quinn

earthaccess: making things simpler

earthaccess is a Python library that simplifies data discovery and access to NASA Earthdata by providing an easy to use library to interface with NASA's authentication and search APIs so that science can be done using less code.

```
import earthaccess
import xarray as xr

auth = earthaccess.login()

results = earthaccess.search_data(
    doi="10.3334/ORNLDAAC/2056",
    bounding_box=(-110,20,-90,40),
    temporal=(2010,2020)
)

ds = xr.open_mfdataset(earthaccess.open(results))
```

- **Auth:** earthaccess handles authentication with NASA EDL.
- **Search:** earthaccess abstracts NASA's search API (CMR) into a *pythonic* module.
- **Access:** earthaccess can download or open data for both cloud and on-prem hosted datasets **with the same code.**

earthaccess as a community why is it working?

- A mentor team **across** NASA Distributed Active Archive Centers (DAACs) working in an open collaborative space.
- Co-creating and teaching common tutorials **alongside** researchers as they migrate analytical workflows to the cloud.
- Reaching out and get involved with different organizations that share the same vision, **grassroots** not just at the top level.
- (Funded) **open source** works, federal agencies need to embrace it.

earthaccess aims to be a technical and social bridge between NASA Earthdata and scientific research.

Reproducibility with less code makes open science more accessible.

earthaccess: it's the community!

Not pictured: more people!

Thank You!

- Fostering new contributions through small group work aligning around specific topics or features. Please reach out if you are interested in joining!
- See our [announcement](#) and [ongoing discussions](#) for more info.

<https://github.com/nsidc/earthaccess>